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**Towards Understanding Compromise
as a Means of Conflict Resolution: An
Exegesis of Genesis 13:8-9**

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Abstract

Conflict is inevitable in any society. Compromise has been identified as one of the means of conflict resolution. This paper aims at looking at compromise as a means of conflict resolution through an exegetical explanation of the event in Genesis 13:8-9. In the two biblical verses, it was discovered that Abraham (in particular) and Lot explored compromise to resolve the conflict that arose among their herders and parted ways amicably. Some supporting views of people are also presented in the paper before conclusion and some recommendations are made. It is concluded that people in conflict can explore compromise as a means of conflict resolution to reach a concession. It is, therefore, recommended that stakeholders in conflict resolution and peace study as well as other people who have an interest in resolving conflicts should always explore compromise as they explore other means of conflict resolution.

Keywords: compromise, conflict resolution, Genesis 13:8-9, Goal 16 of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations, peaceful coexistence

Introduction

The term, conflict, can be described as a disagreement between two parties over an idea, ownership, or object. Conflicts are an integral part of human existence. They are inevitable, even in the case of intrapersonal conflicts, and talk less of interpersonal or intergroup conflicts. These conflicts have to be resolved to have the desirable peaceful coexistence among people. This is to achieve Goal Number Sixteen of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which has to do with “peaceful and non-violent societies.”¹ There have been many definitions of conflict resolution by many scholars. Simply, conflict resolution is a process of resolving disputes or disagreements. Conflict resolution aims at finding a peaceful solution or middle ground for warring factions. It sometimes involves compromise, negotiation, mediation, or diplomacy.

One of the means of conflict resolution is compromise. Compromise can be understood as a way of finding a consensus or reaching an agreement through mutual concessions. It entails surrendering some of one’s likings or inclinations to satisfy others. Compromise plays a significant role in resolving conflicts in that a balance is sought between conflicting parties or interests and reaching a concession that is acceptable to all parties involved in the conflict. In the words of Vojvodic, Martinovic and Pusic (2019), “people who are prone to use compromising style [of conflict resolution] believe that it is better to get something rather than nothing”.² These scholars also assert that “compromise tends to foster better relationship than competition, but not as well as it is in the case of collaboration.”²

This article aims to look at comprise as a means of conflict resolution through an exegetical explanation of the event in Genesis 13:8-9. Some supporting views of people are also presented in the paper before conclusion and some recommendations are made.

¹ O. Gaffney (2014). “Sustainable Development Goals: Improving Human and Planetary Wellbeing.” *Global Change*, 82, May 2014, 20. Available Online: <http://www.igbp.net/download/18.62dc35801456272b46d51/1399290813740/NL82-SDGs.pdf>

² Vojvodic, K., Martinovic, M., & Pusic, A. (2019). "Compromise Or Else: Managing Conflicts in the Negotiation Process." *40th International Scientific Conference on Economic and Social Development*, Buenos Aires, 10-11 May 2019, 39.

An Exegesis of Genesis 13:8-9

WTT Genesis 13:8

וַיֹּאמֶר אַבְרָם אֶל-לוֹט אֶל-נָא תְהִי מְרִיבָה בֵּינִי וּבֵינְךָ וּבֵין רַעֲיֵי וּבֵין רַעֲיֵיךָ כִּי-אֲנָשִׁים אַחִים אָנֹכִי:

NAS Genesis 13:8 Then Abram said to Lot, "Please let there be no strife between you and me, nor between my herdsmen and your herdsmen, for we are brothers.

WTT Genesis 13:9

הֲלֹא כָל-הָאָרֶץ לְפָנֶיךָ הִפְרָד נָא מַעְלֵי אִם-הִשְׁמָאֵל וְאִמְנָה וְאִם-הִימִין וְאִשְׁמְאִילָה:

NAS Genesis 13:9 "Is not the whole land before you? Please separate from me: if *to* the left, then I will go to the right; or if *to* the right, then I will go to the left."

From the text above, Abraham was facing a dangerous outcome of an already existing conflict between his herdsmen and the herdsmen of his nephew, Lot. As he observed and being the head of the family, he moved into action and his actions can be seen in the choice of his words while addressing Lot from the text thus; אֶל-נָא תְהִי מְרִיבָה = "...Please let there be no strife". The combination of the two particles indicates that there is a burning issue on the ground that demands urgent action. The "אֶל-נָא" combination expresses the situation at hand as a complex one that needs urgent solution without delay. But by any means delay occurs the matter can cause unrepairable damage which may include loss of lives and properties. The particle אֶל when used alone is a negative adverbial particle used in Hebrew for request or prohibition with its object as a verb. The usage is emphatic and it goes along with an imperative verb where it becomes a command. The particle נָא is an interjection particle of homonym in Hebrew. It is also an enclitic particle of urgency. It has no specific word for its translation. It can either be translated as "please or listen to me". It also takes an imperative verb as its object. When it is attached to a verb, it expresses entreaty or admonition. It goes with an imperative verb to denote command.³

The combination of the two particles suggests that Abraham was in a tight situation that needed an urgent solution. Even though the usage of the particles appeared to look in a soft tone, both carried strong negation as well

³ BDB "אֶל-נָא" (2010 printed edition), 39 §408 II

as a persuasive command that gave no alternative to Lot other than to comply with Abraham's demand.

מְרִיבָה (*M^e ribah*) is a noun translated as "strife, quarrel, dispute, case, contentions and cause". The noun has a cognate only in Aramaic. It occurred 60 times in the bible. The noun "*rib*" is used for conflicts outside the realm of law cases and courts. Its first occurrence is in Genesis 13:7-8 where 'contention' occurred between the herdsmen before open fighting between the two parties. The term "*rib*" sometimes represents a dispute between two parties. This 'dispute' is set in the context of a mutual law structure binding both parties and a court which is empowered to decide and execute justice. This can be seen in the case of Moses and the Israelites when Israelites quarreled with Moses asserting that he did not keep his end of the bargain by adequately providing for them. Moses then appealed to the Judge, who in turn vindicated him by sending water from a rock smitten by Moses (Exodus 17:7) and decided who was the guilty party, Moses or Israelites. The contention may also be between two individuals as in Deuteronomy 25:1 where the two disputants go to court. Other passages include Isaiah 1:23 and Proverbs 25:8-9. The noun, therefore, occurs very rarely, it occurred only twice and it means "strife" in both places (Genesis 13:8; Numbers 17:14). The other rare cognate is "*yārib*", it occurred three times and it means; disputant, opponent and adversary" (Psalm 35:1; Isaiah 49:25; Jeremiah 18:19)⁴.

The other phrase used by Abraham is קִי־אָנָשִׁים אָנָּחְנוּ which is translated as "...we are men, brothers". This kind of expression in Hebrew is for those who are of the same family or those of the same tribe but is never used in relation to sonship. By this expression, it shows that Abraham and Lot are from the same family. This expression shows that Abraham is still showing some sort of caring for Lot despite the strife between their herdsmen and therefore was willing to bury whatever misunderstanding between their herdsmen.

הִפְרֵד = this is a verb translated as "to divide, separate". It occurred twenty-five (25) times in the Holy Bible. Its first occurrence is Genesis 2:10 where it is used to denote dividing of the river in the Garden of Eden. Its second

⁴ W. E. Vine, et al. (1985). *Vine's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words*. (Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers), 249–250.

occurrence is in the text under consideration (Genesis 13:9) where it expresses the separation of Abraham and Lot. The word often expresses separation of people from each other where sometimes it happens out of hostility as in the case of Jacob and Esau (Genesis 25:23), or as a result of economic status as the case stated in Proverbs 19:4 "...the poor is separated from his neighbor". In a general sense, the verb "pārad", "to separate" carries more negative than positive connotations.⁴ As Abraham continued with his discussion with Lot, he used another word that indicates clearly that Lot stepped on Abraham's nerves. The word נָשָׂא = is translated as "upon me". Abraham's choice of this word shows that from the narrator's point of view, Lot is a burden to Abraham at this point and thus separation was not simply out of convenience but out of necessity. This can be further seen in the inherent use of the negative particle and the particle of interjection of homonym as its antecedent⁵.

Even though the Bible narrative seems to be silent about the whereabouts of Lot when Abraham went to Egypt, the records of the Dead Sea Scrolls of Genesis Apocryphon (20-21) show that Lot not only went alongside Abraham to Egypt but also functioned as a spokesperson to Pharaoh's agents while in Egypt. He acted like the middle man connecting the marriage of Sarah and Pharaoh as he supported the position of Abraham when he said Sarah was his sister. While serving in that capacity, Lot acquired great wealth and he was not only given wealth but was also given an Egyptian woman as his wife as well as male and female servants. Abraham's position on letting Lot choose where he will dwell could be seen in the way he put it to Lot.

נָשָׂא this word is a verb derived from the noun "yāmîn" meaning "to go towards the right hand". Its usage in Genesis 13:9 signifies "direction toward". The word appeared 137 times in the Bible. In its usage in this passage, it is idiomatically used to mean 'southward' since the direction of south is on one's right hand when he faces eastward.⁴ נָשָׂא which is also transliterated as 'sēmōl' is translated as "to go towards the left". Here it is pointing to indicate direction which from the point of Abraham's with Lot points towards the northern part of Canaan. In this regard, Abraham might have been thinking of both of them to remain within the borders of the Promised Land.⁵ The choice of Abraham to use *Hiphil* verbs in directing Lot

⁵ Dan Rickett (2011). "Rethinking the Place and Purpose of Genesis 13." *Journal for the Study of the Old Testament*, (Sage Publication, September 2, 2011), 1 – 24.

to make a choice is to stress the fact that his message to Lot will not be misunderstood but rather it stands as a directive towards a definite point. He stressed his determination of his action to protect his interest which is peaceful co-existence. His expressions are contingent intentions but anything outside that will not be accommodated.⁶

Other Supporting Views on Compromise as a Means of Conflict Resolution

Ndung'u, Mbaro & Okumu (2021) have seen compromise as an essential element in negotiation and mediative dialogue.⁷ Compromise is a great aspect of mediation. Mediation is a process of assisting people in conflict to resolve their differences through the use of a neutral third party, which helps the conflicting parties in attaining a voluntary agreement. In pastoral counselling, the pastor is the arbiter who counsels the conflicting parties on what to do on how the conflicting would be settled. This is rather a conciliatory role. However, in mediation, the mediator assists the conflicting parties in reaching a compromise in resolving their conflict.⁸ This difference (and somehow relationship) was explained further by Nabwire (2016) in a study.⁹ In settlement mediation, disputing parties are encouraged to compromise to settle the conflicts between them and have a peaceful co-existence.¹⁰

⁶ W. Gesenius (2006). *Gesenius' Hebrew Grammar*. (Mineola: Dover Publication INC, 2006 revised), 319-320 §107-108

⁷ M. W. Ndung'u, P. Mbaro, & J. Okumu (2021). "Effectiveness of Negotiation in Resolving Family Conflict: Case of Kajiado North Sub-County, Kenya." *Journal of Research Innovation and Implications in Education*, 5(3), 215-224. Available Online: <https://jriiejournal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/JRIIE-5-3-021.pdf>

⁸ A. O. Afolaranmi (2022). "Use of Social Media for Sustainable Peace by Church Pastors of the Nigerian Baptist Convention, 2010-2020." A PhD thesis submitted to the Department of Politics and International Relations, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, 145.

⁹ C. J. Nabwire (2016). "Utilization and Effectiveness of Pastoral Counselling in the Management of Conflicts in Mainstream and Pentecostal Churches in Nakuru County, Kenya." A PhD thesis submitted to Graduate School of Egerton University.

¹⁰ A. M. Hamza & M. Todorovic (2017). "Peaceful Settlement of Disputes." *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*, 6(1), January-February 2017, 11-

In a study carried out by one of these writers,⁸ one of the respondents identified reaching compromise as an attempt to resolving conflicts among conflicting parties. In the words of this respondent, “I make efforts to let the conflicting people reach a point of ‘give and take.’”¹¹ In this situation, Howell (2014) opined that “the parties accept that there are times when one must be ready to set apart individual wants and needs in preference for others in order to find a ‘common ground’.”¹²

Although compromise as a means of conflict resolution strategy has not been giving desirable results in resolving religious conflicts in Nigeria, especially in interfaith situation as asserted by Ogbuehi (2016)¹³, compromise has been working for resolving conflicts among church members because “they share the common beliefs.”¹¹ Afolaranmi (2021) has emphasized this issue of “give and take” in asserting that “there is no conflict resolution strategy that can work in any situation where every parting in a conflict is insisting to have his/her way.”¹⁴

Conclusion

Compromise is one of the good means of resolving conflicts and promoting peaceful coexistence. As Abraham and Lot explored in the exegetical biblical verses in this paper and parted ways amicably, people in conflicts can also explore this means of conflict resolution and reach a concession as one

17. Available Online: <https://www.longdom.org/articles/peaceful-settlement-of-disputes.pdf>

¹¹ Samuel AK Olaleye, interview by one of the researchers, Ibadan, June 2, 2021.

¹² S. E. Howell (2014). “Conflict Management: A Literature Review and Study.” *Radiology Management*, September/October 2014. Available Online: http://www.ahra.org/AM/Downloads/OI/qc/RM365_p14-23_Features.pdf

¹³ F. I. Ogbuehi (2016). “Critical Appraisal of Dialogue as a Strategy for Religious Conflict Resolution in Nigeria.” *Journal of Religion and Human Relations*, 8(2), 167-168.

¹⁴ A. O. Afolaranmi (2021). “Conflict Resolution Strategies in Resolving Religious Conflict in Nigeria.” *Academia Letters*. Article 874. Available Online: <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL874>

conflicting party ‘gives’ some aspects of their interests and ‘takes’ some aspects of the interests of the other conflicting party.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion above, it is recommended that:

1. Stakeholders in conflict resolution and peace study as well as other people who have an interest in resolving conflicts should always explore compromise as they explore other means of conflict resolution.
2. Conflicting parties should be ready to reach a consensus as they mutually agree to surrender some aspects of their interests and take some aspects of the interests of the other conflicting parties.

This will likely achieve Goal Number Sixteen of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations which aims at peaceful and non-violent societies before 2030.

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